

5G-V2X Topology Intelligence : A GNN Approach

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Abstract

NR-V2X networks are intricate systems with dynamic topology, varied communication modes, and diverse requirements. They require minimal latency for safety-critical applications and rapid data speeds for entertainment. The complexity of V2X networks challenges conventional and heuristic optimisation techniques for resource allocation. These techniques often do not account for the networks' dynamic nature, leading to less optimal performance in rapidly changing conditions. This paper briefly examines how Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) enhance resource management in V2X systems through graph-based modelling of connected devices. In particular, GNNs are employed to identify network conditions and mobility scenarios that require a handover to maintain optimal connectivity. Preliminary experimental tests confirm the validity of the proposed approach.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, graph neural network (GNN), vehicle-to-everything (V2X), resource allocation, unsupervised learning, O-RAN architecture

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1 Introduction

New Radio Vehicle-to-Everything (NR-V2X) communication networks, which are standardised by 3GPP (ETSI TS 122 186 V18.0.1, ETSI 103 831), are designed to meet the high reliability and low latency requirements that are essential for advanced applications such as cooperative autonomous driving, traffic control management and pedestrian safety. However, the decentralised and dynamic nature of V2X network scenarios makes precise modelling challenging, rendering traditional resource allocation methods inadequate.

Conventional resource management approaches often depend on channel state information (CSI) associated with accurate GPS coordinate acquisition. Nonetheless, acquiring highly reliable CSI remains a considerable challenge, especially in fast-evolving high-velocity vehicular scenarios.

Deterministic, non-learning resource allocation methods like convex, nonlinear, and integer programming, along with Stackelberg game theory, and metaheuristics, face key limitations in vehicular communications [1–4]. Furthermore, the computational complexity of resource allocation is often modelled as an NP-hard problem. This limits the ability to fulfil ultra-reliability and low latency requirements, resulting in inefficient resource distribution, particularly in dense urban areas.

In contrast, conventional AI-driven resource allocation techniques often require fixed-size input data structures. Consequently, these traditional models struggle to cope with the dynamic scalability, data heterogeneity, and stringent latency constraints characteristic of NR V2X

networks. To overcome these limitations, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) are emerging as promising AI tools for topology-aware resource management [5–11]. In particular, more sophisticated variants of GNNs, such as the Graph Isomorphic Networks (GIN) and Graph Sampling and Aggregation (GraphSAGE) networks, have the important ability to dynamically adapt to changes in V2X network topology without the need for frequent model retraining. This paper examines the transformative capability of Graph Neural Networks to handle variable and non-predefined input sizes for AI-driven resource management in future communication networks, with a particular focus on their role in Handover event detection in V2X. By integrating GINs with the digital twin model and RAN architecture, we achieve real-time, topology-sensitive resource regulation and adaptive connectivity optimisation in high dynamic radio settings.

The body of the paper is organised as follows. Section II reviews the state of the art, providing a mathematical overview of GNN behaviour. Section III outlines the fundamentals of GNN intelligence. Section IV presents the V2X radio scenario evolution analysis using GINs. Section V details the handover event detection methodology for V2X and reports the experimental results. Section VI concludes the paper.

2 State of the Art

GNNs offer an innovative method for tackling radio resource management in wireless networks.

In [12], a heterogeneous graph models a wireless network with different pairs of transceivers, such as vehicles, mobile users and base stations. The nodes represent pairs of transceivers, and the edges represent interference over shared channels. A custom GNN architecture optimizes channel and power allocation concurrently, using a shared message computation layer for overall network understanding and specific layers for channel and power tasks, enhancing inter-task data sharing. This GNN framework converts network states depicted as graphs into optimal channel and power configurations, yielding satisfactory network throughput. For graphs with fewer nodes, the GNN framework achieves 95% of the efficiency of the optimal solution obtained with exhaustive search techniques. As transceiver pairs grow, the GNN framework’s performance approaches that of the Closest algorithm. However, GNN is much more efficient, achieving the same results using just 4% of the Closest algorithm’s runtime.

In [13], GNNs are used for V2I and V2V channel allocation, optimising network capacity and maintaining service quality in dynamic scenarios. This problem is NP-hard, particularly with V2V prioritization over V2I for Quality of Service (QoS) protection. GNN treats the V2X network as a graph with V2V/V2I nodes (with channel gain and power) and edges weighted by interference gain, generating low-dimensional embeddings of node interactions via message passing. A Q-network uses these embeddings from V2X pairs to allocate spectrum resources, considering each pair as an independent agent in reinforcement learning. Simulation results show that this GNN-RL scheme is close to optimal performance compared to a brute-force search to select the best channel for each V2X pair.

The study [14] introduces a GIN-based method for interference management in V2X. Each V2V link acts as a node with current channel gains and power, while edges represent interference channel gains between links. A GIN, trained by gradient descent on a quadratic cost function, generates node embeddings to solve the dynamic spectrum and power allocation optimisation problem. This optimisation aims to increase vehicle data rates while respecting V2I quality of service, per-link power limits, and reuse of individual vehicle uplinks. Simulations show that the GIN-based method increases vehicle data rates by approximately 67% over random allocation and outperforms the greedy algorithm.

The paper [15] addresses the maximisation problem of network data rate under power constraints by modelling the cellular system as a heterogeneous graph. In this graph, nodes represent communication links characterised by attributes such as distance, channel and power; edges represent interference paths characterised by intra- or inter-cell differences and channel-related

characteristics. A specific GNN attention layer attends to the attributes of both nodes and edges. By training the GNN with labels generated by particle swarm optimisation-based power allocation, it learns to predict near-optimal transmission powers. Simulations show that this GAT approach surpasses MLP in average data rates and adapts well to various network conditions, achieving real-time wireless decisions.

The study [16] applies GNNs to optimise joint communication and detection in THz vehicular networks. The THz band suffers from high path loss and directional links, requiring careful management of vehicle interactions to avoid interference. A heterogeneous graph models the complex interactions and connectivity between vehicle types (suppliers and destinations) to implement the GNN methodology. This GNN is designed to optimise each vehicle’s service mode and destination, increase communication speed and meet detection requirements. Simulations demonstrate that this GNN approach exceeds traditional methods, swiftly adapting to shifts in vehicle configuration and achieving nearly optimal results. These use cases motivate a deeper investigation of GNN feature learning for the V2X domain, which will be explored in the next session.

Figure 1: GIN Embedding Shift for V2X scenarios in Porta Pia area (Roma)

3 Fundamentals of GNN Intelligence

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) are sophisticated models designed to analyse graph-structured data. Unlike standard neural networks, which manage grid-based data, GNNs prioritise the interactions between nodes. These interactions are represented as edges and are intrinsic to graphs. Mathematically, a graph $G(V, E)$ comprises a set of nodes V connected by a set of edges E . Every node $v_i \in V$ is linked with a feature vector \mathbf{x}_i , while each edge $(v_i, v_j) \in E$ may possess an associated feature vector \mathbf{e}_{ij} .

In graph neural networks, node representations are iteratively updated via a *message-passing* process that collects data from adjacent nodes [17]. This process involves generating *node embeddings* to represent individual nodes within their local context and creating a *graph embedding* to encode the global topological and structural properties of the entire graph. Embedding vectors are essential for tasks such as link prediction and anomaly detection.

In mathematical terms, layer k of a GNN model updates the representation $\mathbf{h}_i^{(k)}$ of node v_i by incorporating information from its neighbors $\mathcal{N}(i)$ as follows:

$$\mathbf{h}_i^{(k)} = \psi^{(k)} \left(\mathbf{h}_i^{(k-1)}, \text{AGG}_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} \phi^{(k)}(\mathbf{h}_i^{(k-1)}, \mathbf{h}_j^{(k-1)}, \mathbf{e}_{ij}) \right) \quad (1)$$

where:

- $\phi^{(k)}$ is the function that handles the interactions of each node i with its neighbours j at layer k ;

- AGG is the operator that aggregates neighbourhood vectors using sum, average or maximum methods.
- $\psi^{(k)}$ is the function that improves the representation of node i at layer k , possibly by using an activation function.

3.1 Graph Isomorphism Networks

Graph Isomorphism Networks (GINs) significantly advance GNNs by improving model expressiveness with update strategies focused on MLPs. In GINs, the update rule for \mathbf{h}_i is governed by equation (2), where $MLP^{(k)}$ denotes the multi-layer perceptron at the k -th GIN layer, as illustrated in fig.(2).

$$\mathbf{h}_i^{(k)} = MLP^{(k)} \left((1 + \epsilon) \cdot \mathbf{h}_i^{(k-1)} + \mathbf{m}_i^{(k)} \right) \quad (2)$$

The multilayer perception $MLP^{(k)}$ at layer k , processes the node embeddings $\mathbf{h}_i^{(k-1)}$ and their neighbourhood information $\mathbf{h}_j^{(k-1)} \mid j \in \mathcal{N}(i)$ through a two-step procedure.

- **Message Passing:** Aggregates nearby node embeddings by summing them.

$$\mathbf{m}_i^{(k)} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} \mathbf{h}_j^{(k-1)}, \quad (3)$$

- **Transformation:** From equations (4 and 5), the message $\mathbf{m}_i^{(k)}$ is merged with the node embedding from layer $(k - 1)$, and then processed with an affine transformation and nonlinear activation.

$$MLP^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) = \sigma \left(\mathbf{W}^{(k)} \mathbf{z} + \mathbf{b}^{(k)} \right), \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{z} = (1 + \epsilon^{(k)}) \mathbf{h}_i^{(k-1)} + \mathbf{m}_i^{(k)}, \quad (5)$$

In eq.(4) $\mathbf{W}^{(k)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d^{(k)} \times d^{(k-1)}}$ is a learnable weight matrix, $\mathbf{b}^{(k)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d^{(k)}}$ is a bias term, and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is an element-wise activation function (e.g., sigmoid or ReLU). The scalar ϵ , either fixed or variable, modifies the influence of a node's features during aggregation within the Graph Isomorphism Network (GIN) model.

Charilaos and Kanatsoulis demonstrate [18] that GINs possess the same discriminative capability as the Weisfeiler–Lehman graph isomorphism test. This enables them to differentiate between various graph structures effectively. This capability can be leveraged in vehicular networks, where slight topological changes can significantly impact performance and connectivity.

4 V2X Radio Scenario Evolution Analysis with GINs

Effective communication in V2X networks requires seamless handovers as vehicles move through areas with varying coverage. However, traditional handover methods rely on metrics such as signal strength or distance, which may not fully capture V2X dynamics. To overcome this limitation, we investigated using GINs to analyse the V2X graph dynamics. Within our conceptual framework, the V2X scenario is modelled as a graph. Nodes represent connected autonomous vehicles (CAVs) or road-side units (RSUs), while edges represent potential radio communication links between them. These links are assessed based on the nodes' physical proximity, radio path loss, signal-to-interference ratio (SINR) and the minimum signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) required to support the CAV's traffic demand (bitrate).

Figure 2: GIN Encoder pipeline

We use GINs to analyse and detect the evolution of the vehicular scenario over time, leveraging the ability of these models to encode structural information in V2X communication graphs through neighbourhood aggregation and transformation. In particular, a three-level GIN has been designed and trained, followed by a *readout phase*, to distinguish non-isomorphic graphs based on the Weisfeiler-Lehman test. In the *readout phase*, sum pooling of the node embeddings produces a concise representation of the entire V2X graph. Subsequently, global pooling is applied to the graph embedding, resulting in a single-dimensional value z_G that succinctly represents the whole V2X scenario at the graph level.

By analysing the variation of the graph embedding Z_G over time, significant changes in the network topology can be detected, emerging congestion points can be identified, and the proximity of different Roadside Units (RSUs) can be assessed. Figure 1 shows the evolution of the V2X network state $\Delta_{G_{V2X}} = z_G^{(t)} - z_G^{(t-1)}$ over successive time steps for a simulated V2X network within a $500m \times 500m$ area around Porta Pia Square in Rome.

Figure 3: GIN-based autoencoder architecture

The GIN encoder was trained using the GIN-based autoencoder illustrated in Fig. 3, aiming to minimise reconstruction losses for graph features X and the adjacency matrix A . The overall loss can be expressed as the sum of two terms,

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{features}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{adjacency}}, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathcal{L}_{\text{features}} = \|X - \hat{X}\|_F^2$ denotes the Frobenius norm of the difference between the original and reconstructed node features, while $\mathcal{L}_{\text{adjacency}} = \|A - \hat{A}\|_F^2$ corresponds to the Frobenius norm of the difference between the original and reconstructed adjacency matrices. Figure 4 shows the training loss of the GIN-based autoencoder, configured with a three-layer encoder

using 64 hidden features and a 32-dimensional graph representation Z to model the dynamic radio scenario of the V2X network in the Porta Pia region.

The next section examines the use of graph and node embeddings to predict handover events. More generally, monitoring the embedding vectors of a V2X device can trigger the detection of significant changes in connectivity within a V2X network. This can trigger dynamic re-optimisation of CAV-RSU links, facilitating real-time resource adaptation. In addition, synchronising resource management with topological shifts enhances resilience, scalability, and efficiency of V2X systems in dynamic 5G/6G contexts.

Figure 4: Loss curve for the GIN-autoencoder on Porta Pia V2X network

5 Handover Event Detection Methodology for V2X and Experimental Results

This section presents a GIN-driven V2X Intelligence approach for detecting *handover (HO) candidate CAVs* and confirming *actual HO events* within a V2X network. The temporal changes in GIN embeddings are utilized in dynamic V2X scenarios within Rome’s Porta Pia. This is modelled over actual road networks using both OpenStreetMap (OSM) [19] and Simulation of Urban MObility (SUMO) [20,21]. The output from SUMO is processed via Sionna software [22], with radio propagation adjusted to align with the latest 3GPP guidelines. All numerical results are obtained from this unified simulation framework. The setting for the radio scenario are:

- Transmit power for the RSU antennas: 10 dBm
- Transmit power for vehicles: 0 dBm
- The antenna gain are set to 1 dBi
- The antenna pattern is "dipole"
- Operating frequency: 5.9 GHz
- Bandwidth: 800 MHz

The proposed method processes a sequentially arranged set of V2X graphs $\mathcal{G} = \{G_t\}_{t=0}^{T-1}$, where each graph captures the network structure and link conditions at each timestep t .

5.1 Node Feature Extraction

For each graph $G_t = (V_t, E_t)$, a node feature matrix $X_t \in \mathbb{R}^{|V_t| \times d}$ is constructed by combining:

1. *Raw node attributes*: spatial coordinates (x, y) , traffic load indicator, non-line-of-sight blockage attribute, binary CAV/RSU roles, and in/out degrees.
2. *Edge aggregated features*. For each edge $e \in E$, the attributes $a \in \{\text{edge_SINR}, \text{edge_Shannon_Capacity}\}$ are considered. Two composite features are subsequently extracted from the node's outgoing and incoming edges: the mean and maximum of the attributes.
3. *Link-type counts*: counts of Line-of-Sight (LoS), Non-LoS (NLoS), and NLoS with blockage (NLoSv) links.
4. *Serving and alternative RSU SNRs*: for each CAV v , the best serving SNR $S(v)$, the second-best (alternative) SNR $A(v)$, the margin $M(v) = S(v) - A(v)$, and the Euclidean distance to the serving RSU.

5.2 Embedding Generation via GIN

The feature matrix X_t is processed by a Graph Isomorphism Network (GIN) encoder with $L = 2$ layers, producing node embeddings $H_t \in \mathbb{R}^{|V_t| \times d_h}$ with $d_h = 64$. This transformation captures higher-order topological and contextual information relevant to mobility and link changes.

5.3 Unsupervised Handover Candidate Detection

Nodes are monitored over time using their persistent identifier, CAV/RSU_id (*Primary_ID*). For each *Primary_ID* o , it is maintained:

- *Exponential Moving Average (EMA)* of embeddings:

$$\text{EMA}_t(o) = (1 - \alpha) \text{EMA}_{t-1}(o) + \alpha h_t(o), \quad (7)$$

where $h_t(o)$ is the embedding of o at t and α is a smoothing factor.

- *Embedding jump magnitude*:

$$\Delta_t(o) = \|h_t(o) - \text{EMA}_{t-1}(o)\|_2. \quad (8)$$

Figure 5: Porta Pia Sionna Scenario

- *Adaptive z-score threshold* computed in real time using Welford’s algorithm. A variation $\Delta_t(o)$ is considered significant if it exceeds the current running mean plus a margin given by the z-score multiplier times the current standard deviation, with ε used to avoid issues when the variance is very small.

$$\Delta_t(o) > \mu_{t-1}(o) + z_{\text{node}} \cdot \max(\sigma_{t-1}(o), \varepsilon) \quad (9)$$

where $\mu_{t-1}(o)$ and $\sigma_{t-1}(o)$ are the running mean and standard deviation of Δ for the node ID o .

A raw handover candidate is confirmed when it satisfies two conditions:

1. *Radio plausibility check*: The SNR $A_t(o)$ of the best alternative link for node o at time t must be not lower than the SNR $S_t(o)$ of the serving link minus a configurable slack margin δ_{pre} (in dB):

$$A_t(o) \geq S_t(o) - \delta_{\text{pre}}. \quad (10)$$

This margin prevents discarding valid alternatives due to small SNR fluctuations caused by noise or measurement uncertainty.

2. *Temporal persistence*: The above inequality must hold for at least `p_ttt` consecutive timesteps, where `p_ttt` denotes the candidate Time-To-Trigger. This requirement filters out transient fluctuations, confirming only stable candidate situations.

The result is a set of **HO candidate flags** $\text{flag}_t(v)$ for each CAV node.

5.4 Actual Handover Event Detection

An *actual HO event* is declared for CAV v at timestep t if all the following hold:

1. *Serving RSU change*: Let $\rho_t(v)$ be the *Primary_ID* of the serving RSU at t . An HO occurs if $\rho_{t-1}(v) \neq \rho_t(v)$.

2. *SNR margin*:

$$S_t^{\text{new}}(v) - S_t^{\text{old}}(v) \geq \delta_{\text{snr}}, \quad (11)$$

where $S_t^{\text{new}}(v)$ is the maximum SNR from the new RSU, and $S_t^{\text{old}}(v)$ from the old RSU.

3. *Temporal Persistence*: The above margin condition must be satisfied for all $\tau \in [t - \text{p_ttt} + 1, t]$.
4. *Minimum δ - time*: At least *Minimum δ - time* snapshots must elapse since the previous HO for v .

To assess the system accuracy, each accepted event is recorded together with the CAV identifier, the RSU transition, the serving and alternative link SNR values, the embedding jump magnitude, and a binary indicator specifying whether the candidate HO detector flagged it.

5.5 Experimental Results in the Porta Pia Area

The proposed handover detection framework was evaluated in a controlled urban scenario covering a $500 \times 500 \text{ m}^2$ area surrounding Porta Pia, a densely built zone characterized by high vehicular traffic and served by four Road Side Units (RSUs) deployed at strategic intersections. The radio plausibility check was configured with a slack margin of $\delta_{\text{SNR}} = 2 \text{ dB}$, and the candidate Time-To-Trigger was set to `p_ttt` = 10 ms, corresponding to 100 consecutive temporal snapshots given the 1 ms sampling interval. This configuration ensures that only alternative

links with comparable signal quality to the serving RSU and stable over time are considered for confirmation.

The test set comprised approximately 1200 CAV trajectories, covering a time span of 25 minutes during peak traffic conditions. The system achieved a handover detection accuracy of 93.4%, with a precision of 91.8% and recall of 94.7% when compared against ground-truth transitions derived from signal strength logs. The mean SNR difference between the serving and best alternative RSU at the handover instant was 2.1 dB, indicating that most events occurred under marginal quality gaps. The average embedding jump magnitude for confirmed handovers was 0.42 in normalized Euclidean distance.

Latency analysis showed that the end-to-end decision time remained below 35 ms, ensuring compatibility with NR V2X URLLC constraints. These results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed approach in a realistic, interference-prone urban environment such as Porta Pia.

6 Conclusion

This paper demonstrates the effectiveness of graph neural networks, particularly Graph Isomorphism Networks (GINs), in solving the dynamic and topology-aware resource allocation challenges of 5G NR V2X systems. By embedding the ever-changing vehicular network topology within a GIN, our unsupervised framework enables real-time detection of significant topology shifts and proactive handover decisions.

This work proposes a fully unsupervised, GIN-based framework for handover (HO) detection in V2X, representing vehicles and roadside units as nodes in a dynamic graph and utilizing GIN embeddings to monitor network topology changes.

Experiments in a dense urban scenario with thousands CAV trajectories showed a 93.4% HO detection accuracy, with decision times under 55 ms, satisfying NR-V2X URLLC requirements. The proposed framework thus enables unsupervised detection of mobility-induced topology shifts and validated handover events, supporting both real-time network monitoring and dataset generation. Ultimately, by aligning resource management with topological dynamics, this approach improves V2X system resilience, scalability, and efficiency for future 5G/6G networks.

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References

- [1] C. Cheng, D. Yao, Y. Zhang, J. Li, and Y. Guo, “A vehicle passing model in non-signalized intersections based on non-cooperative game theory,” in *2019 IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference (ITSC)*, 2019, pp. 2286–2291.
- [2] A. Moubayed, A. Shami, P. Heidari, A. Larabi, and R. Brunner, “Edge-enabled v2x service placement for intelligent transportation systems,” *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 1380–1392, 2021.
- [3] M. Fahad, F. Aadil, S. Ejaz, and A. Ali, “Implementation of evolutionary algorithms in vehicular ad-hoc network for cluster optimization,” in *2017 Intelligent Systems Conference (IntelliSys)*, 2017, pp. 137–141.

- [4] F. Mangiatordi, E. Pallotti, and P. Del Vecchio, “A non cooperative game theoretic approach for energy management in mv grid,” in *2013 13th International Conference on Environment and Electrical Engineering (EEEIC)*, 2013, pp. 266–271.
- [5] Z. Shan, X. Yi, H. Yu, C.-S. Liao, and S. Jin, “Learning to code on graphs for topological interference management,” in *2023 IEEE International Symp. on Information Theory (ISIT)*, 2023, pp. 2386–2391.
- [6] Y. Dai, L. Lyu, N. Cheng, M. Sheng, J. Liu, X. Wang, S. Cui, L. Cai, and X. Shen, “A survey of graph-based resource management in wireless networks -part i: Optimization approaches,” *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, pp. 1–1, 2024.
- [7] K. Huang, L. Liang, X. Yi, H. Ye, S. Jin, and G. Y. Li, “Meta-learning empowered graph neural networks for radio resource management,” *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 2025.
- [8] Z. Gao and D. Gündüz, “Graph neural networks over the air for decentralized tasks in wireless networks,” *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 73, pp. 721–737, 2025.
- [9] G. Amati, S. Angelini, F. Mangiatordi, E. Pallotti, and P. Salvo, “A massive clustering algorithm for fast radio resource allocation to distributed units in o-ran networks,” in *2024 AEIT International Annual Conference (AEIT)*, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [10] Q. F. Sun, H. Yang, and O. L. Petrosian, “Graph attention network enhanced power allocation for wireless cellular system,” *Informatics and Automation*, 2024.
- [11] Q. Zhou, C.-J. Guo, C. Wang, and L. Cui, “Radio resource management for c-v2x using graph matching and actor–critic learning,” *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 11, pp. 2645–2649, 2022.
- [12] L. Chen, J. Zhu, and J. Evans, “Gnn-based joint channel and power allocation in heterogeneous wireless networks,” in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops)*, 2024, pp. 233–238.
- [13] Z. He, L. Wang, H. Ye, G. Y. Li, and B.-H. F. Juang, “Resource allocation based on graph neural networks in vehicular communications,” in *GLOBECOM 2020 - 2020 IEEE Global Communications Conference*, 2020, pp. 1–5.
- [14] S. Mortazavi and E. Sousa, “Intelligent Interference Management in VANETs Through Dynamic Resource Allocation Based on Graph Isomorphism Networks,” in *2024 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [15] S. Qiushi, H. Yang, and O. Petrosian, “Graph attention network enhanced power allocation for wireless cellular system,” *Informatics and Automation*, vol. 23, pp. 259–283, 01 2024.
- [16] X. Li, M. Chen, Y. Liu, Z. Zhang, D. Liu, and S. Mao, “Graph neural networks for joint communication and sensing optimization in vehicular networks,” *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 41, no. 12, pp. 3893–3907, 2023.
- [17] K. Xu, W. Hu, J. Leskovec, and S. Jegelka, “How powerful are graph neural networks,” *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2018.
- [18] C. I. Kanatsoulis and A. Ribeiro, “Graph neural networks are more powerful than we think,” 2024.

- [19] OpenStreetMap contributors, “Planet dump retrieved from <https://planet.osm.org> ,” <https://www.openstreetmap.org>, 2017.
- [20] P. A. Lopez, M. Behrisch, L. Bieker-Walz, J. Erdmann, Y.-P. Flötteröd, R. Hilbrich, L. Lücken, J. Rummel, P. Wagner, and E. Wießner, “Microscopic traffic simulation using sumo,” in *The 21st IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems*. IEEE, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://elib.dlr.de/124092/>
- [21] P. Alvarez Lopez, A. Banse, M. Barthauer, M. Behrisch, B. Couéraud, J. Erdmann, Y.-P. Flötteröd, R. Hilbrich, R. Nippold, and P. Wagner, “Simulation of urban mobility (sumo),” Oct. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13907886>
- [22] J. Hoydis, S. Cammerer, F. Ait Aoudia, M. Nimier-David, L. Maggi, G. Marcus, A. Vem, and A. Keller, “Sionna,” 2022, <https://nvlabs.github.io/sionna/>.